

PHASE STUDY IN THE SYSTEM $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-KNO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$

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During the phase study of the system $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-KNO}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ different crops of crystals, separated at different stages of crystallisation, have been analysed. Amongst these are found crystals respectively of the compositions : (i) $4\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (ii) $2\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (iii) $\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, in agreement with the inferences drawn in the previous communication (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 351).

Vartak and Kabadi (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 351) have shown from the study of conductivity and the thermometric titrations the existence of the molecular compounds: (i) $4\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, (ii) $2\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and (iii) $\text{KNO}_2\text{-Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solutions containing potassium nitrite and lead nitrate in different molar concentrations. The present paper describes the phase study of the system containing these two constituents in various molar proportions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The different mixtures containing lead nitrate and potassium nitrite respectively in molar proportions 1:3, 1:2, 1:1, 2:1 and 3:1 were evaporated at room temperature over P_2O_5 in vacuum desiccators. These were evacuated from time to time with Cenco-hyvac pump. At different stages of the process of crystallisation, crops of crystals separated out. After washing them with 80% alcohol and drying over calcium chloride to constant weight, each crop, and the corresponding mother-liquor were analysed for Pb^{2+} , K^+ , NO_2^- and NO_3^- respectively. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

S. No.	Composition of the mother-liquor.	Percentage composition of the crop separated.			Empirical composition Molecular composition	Nature.	
		K. Pb.	NO ₃ .	H ₂ O.		Colour.	Stability.
1.	(i) $3KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	15.51	41.19	27.44	12.32	3.579	Orange-red. Stable in dry air. Absorb moisture from atmosphere very rapidly.
	(ii) $7KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	15.51	41.19	27.44	12.32	3.579	Do Do
	(iii) $4KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	22.64	30.04	26.71	18.00	2.61	Yellowish orange Stable in dry air. Absorb moisture from atmosphere slowly.
2.	(i) $2KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	15.51	41.19	27.44	12.32	3.579	Orange-red. Stable in dry air. Absorb moisture from atmosphere very rapidly.
	(ii) $K_2Pb_2(NO_3)_5$	15.51	41.19	27.44	12.32	3.579	Do Do
	(iii) $2KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	15.03	39.88	17.72	23.89	3.486	Yellowish orange Stable at room temperature in dry atmosphere. Absorb moisture slowly from atmosphere.
3.	(i) $KNO_3 + Pb(NO_3)_2$	15.03	39.87	17.72	23.89	3.489	Do Do
	(ii) $6KNO_3 + 7Pb(NO_3)_2$	9.59	50.20	9.16	33.10	...	Lemon-yellow Stable at room temperature. Practically unaffected by atmospheric moisture.

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Composition of the mother-liquor.	Percentage composition of the crop separated.			Empirical composition Molecular composition	N a t u r e.		
		K.	Pb.	NO ₂ , NO ₃ , H ₂ O.		Colour.	Stability.	
3.	(iii) $K_4Pb_6(NO_2)_4(NO_3)_8$ (NO ₂) ₄	7.874	52.24	13.93	25.03	0.926	Deep yellow crystals	Stable at room temperature in dry atmosphere. Absorb moisture from the atmosphere slowly.
4.	(i) $KNO_2 + 2Pb(NO_2)_2$	...	62.55	...	37.45	...	...	...
	(ii) $2KNO_2 + 3Pb(NO_2)_2$	4.233	56.15	4.992	33.62	0.984	Lemon-yellow	Stable at room temperature. Practically unaffected by the atmospheric moisture.
(iii) $KNO_2 + Pb(NO_2)_2$	8.97	47.61	10.58	28.52	4.32	...	Yellow	Stable at room temperature.
5.	(i) $KNO_2 + 3Pb(NO_2)_2$	...	62.55	...	37.45	...	...	...
	(ii) $3KNO_2 + 5Pb(NO_2)_2$	1.416	60.28	1.671	35.98	0.653	Lemon-yellow	Stable at room temperature. Practically unaffected by atmospheric moisture.
(iii) $3KNO_2 + 2Pb(NO_2)_2$	12.57	44.26	14.78	26.52	1.87	...	Yellow	Stable at room temperature in dry atmosphere. Absorb moisture from the atmosphere slowly.

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Comp. of the mother-liquor.	Mol. comp. of the crystals separated	S. No.	Comp. of the mother-liquor.	Mol. comp. of the crystals separated.
1.	(i) $3\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3.	(ii) $6\text{KNO}_3 + 7\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$4(\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb} \cdot \text{NO}_3)_2$
	(ii) $7\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		(iii) $\text{K}_4\text{Pb}_8(\text{NO}_3)_8(\text{NO}_2)_8$	$2(\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} + 3\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2)$
	(iii) $4\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3(3\text{K}(\text{NO}_3)) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		(i) $\text{KNO}_3 + 2\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
2.	(i) $2\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	4.	(ii) $2\text{KNO}_3 + 3\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} + 4\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
	(ii) $\text{K}_4\text{Pb}_8(\text{NO}_3)_8(\text{NO}_3)_8$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		(iii) $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
	(iii) $2\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$		(i) $\text{KNO}_3 + 3\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
3.	(i) $\text{KNO}_3 + \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.	(ii) $3\text{KNO}_3 + 5\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} + 7\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
				(iii) $3\text{KNO}_3 + 2\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$	$2(\text{Pb} < \frac{\text{NO}_2}{\text{NO}_3} \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O})$

DISCUSSION

In column four of Table I are shown the empirical compositions of the crystals separated in every stage. The closer inspection of this column shows the presence of the crystals having the molecular composition as shown below :

Soln. No.	Crop No.	Comp. of the crystals.	Molar ratio.
1	3	$4\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	4 : 1
2	2	$2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	2 : 1
3	1	$2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	2 : 1
4	3	$\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1 : 1

These results appear to be in agreement with the findings of conductometric and thermometric study of similar solutions, made earlier by the authors (*loc. cit.*).

During similar study of mixtures containing lead nitrate and lead nitrite (to be published later) evidence has been found of the existence of the compound of composition $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. If mixtures in the present investigation are assumed to contain such a compound, the composition of the three compounds, mentioned above, may be expressed in the following manner :

- (i) $4\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \dots \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 6\text{KNO}_3$
 (ii) $2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \dots \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3$
 (iii) $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} \dots \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

It is thus shown that these compounds are the mixed crystals containing $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3$ as a chief constituent. The study of the stability of these compounds and their behaviour regarding the absorption of moisture from atmosphere, which is shown in the last column of Table I, points out some interesting results. The crop $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3$ tends to absorb moisture very slowly from the atmosphere. The mixed crystals containing this compound and potassium nitrite do not appear to be so stable. Actually it has been found that the stability of the compound decreases as the number of potassium nitrite molecules present therein increases. The mixed crystals containing lead nitrate are found to be more stable and do not absorb any moisture. The crop (iii) of the solution (3) has the composition $\text{K}_5\text{Pb}_5(\text{NO}_2)_4(\text{NO}_3)_{11}$. The molecular composition of the crop may be expressed as $2[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3] \cdot \text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. The reason for assigning the composition in the bracket has already been given above. Nayar and Pande (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 27A, 284; 1949, 30A, 251) have inferred the existence of the compound, $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, in solution from the study of certain physical properties of the solutions containing lead nitrate and potassium nitrate. It thus appears that these crystals are the mixed crystals containing $2[\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_2)_2 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{KNO}_3]$ and $\text{KNO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. The closer examination of Table I shows that these crystals separated out from the mother-liquor containing an excess of lead nitrate. Potassium nitrate is presumed to have been formed during the reaction.